

EXPRESSION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE DURING THE TIME OF THE TEMURIAN IN PERIOD SOURCES

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Abstract: During the Timurid period, the Uzbek language reached its highest stage of development. Their efforts to use the Uzbek language more in public administration have paid off. The Uzbek language, which is in a high place in state administration and trade, gradually began to gain its place in literature creativity. We can learn about these processes by analyzing the sources created during the Timurid period. In the article, such information is analyzed through Abdurazzak Samarkandi's work "Matlai Sadayn wa Majmai Bahrain" and other additional sources.

Key-words: Amir Timur, Timurids, Uzbek language, Turkic languages, Abdurazzak Samarkandi, "Matlai Sadayn wa Majmai Bahrain", Diplomacy, Embassy, International Relations.

Introduction. Abdurazzoq Samarkandi's work "Matlai sa'dayn a majmai bahrain" is a valuable source for studying social-political, cultural-educational processes of the Timurid period. The analysis of the information in this work, written by a personal witness and participant of the events, is valuable for the reconstruction of historical events. The Uzbek language is one of the ancient languages belonging to the family of Turkic languages, and it occupies a great place in the life of Turks. This language had serious competition with the Persian language during its development. It was not easy for it to develop as a language and find its place. The preservation of the Uzbek language and the fact that more than 50 million people use it as their mother tongue are of great importance to the past dynasties. One such dynasty is the Timurids. They encouraged the widespread use of the Turkish (Uzbek)

language without preventing the preservation, development and equal use of different languages.

The main part. Qutb, Saifi Saroi, Haidar Khorazmi, Durbek, Amiri, Atoi, Sakkoki, Lutfi, Babur, Muhammad Salih and others lived and worked during this period. Especially in Movarounnahr and Khorasan, the status of Uzbek language, literature and culture increased. The Turkic-speaking peoples of Khorasan and their intellectuals began to have very close relations with scientists, poets and artists from Samarkand, Bukhara, Turkestan and other cities. Any artist lived and created in any country or city that was convenient for him. For example, the Khorezm poets Haydar and Hafiz Khorezmi went to Shiraz, the poet Sheikh Atoi Ismail Ota's descendants from Turbat (now in the Republic of Kazakhstan, near Tashkent) to Balkh, and Maulana Lutfi, who was originally from Tashkent, went to live near Herat.ⁱ

Despite the fact that during the Timurid era, the development of the Uzbek language increased and a number of creative works were created, the number of artists who created mainly in the Persian language was more. However, we can say that in mutual communication, trade and diplomatic correspondence, the Turkish language was used equally, and in some cases even prevailed. Amir Temur always communicated in Uzbek and addressed his enemies in this language. Samarkand has a separate language of communication, which is based on the half-Turkish and half-Persian languageⁱⁱ. We can learn that the old Uzbek language was widely used in trade and other social spheres in a large area from the travel book of the Russian tourist Afanasy Nikitin called "Khojenie za tri morya". Turkish sentences are often used in it. As a result of communication in this language in India and other eastern countries, it can be said that the traveler himself has mastered the old Uzbek language well.ⁱⁱⁱ

There are many poets in Khorasan and Movarounnahr who write in both Persian and Turkish languages, and literary life flourishes. The attention to the translators of Eastern classical literature has also increased. Works related to literary

theory such as "Chahor Manoliy" were created. The types of artistic creativity such as ghazal, rubai, tuyuq have developed^{iv}.

According to Alisher Navoi, great importance was attached to the development of Turkish literature during the Timurid period. He said that from Amir Timur to the last days of his son Shahrukh Mirza's reign, there were people creating in Turkish. Sakkoki, Haydar Khorezmi, Atoi, Muqimi, Amiri and Gadoi, and to a lesser extent, Lutfiy wrote well in the Turkish language^v.

The letters brought by ambassadors from China in 1412 were written in three languages - Chinese, Persian and Turkish^{vi}. This letter was considered an additional letter to the main letter and was a waybill. A letter written in different languages was of great importance for the ambassadors who passed through the territory of different countries and peoples. The embassy in 1447 appointed to Egypt under the leadership of Abdurazzaq Samarkandi failed to materialize. But its details are explained, and Shahrukh Mirza writes the letter to the ruler of Egypt first in Turkish and Persian, and after checking it with the emirs and intellectuals, he orders it to be translated into Arabic^{vii}. Husayn Boyqaro, being a great lover of the Turkish language, implemented a number of political and cultural activities for the further development of this language in the country, its development and future prosperity.

Conclusion. By studying the information in the sources, we can learn that the contribution of the Timurids to the Uzbek language reaching its current stage, creating valuable works in this language and reaching us.

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